

Neutrinoless Double Beta Decay: where we stand and what lies ahead

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The context: ghostly neutrinos

- The most poorly understood particle within the SM
- First postulated by Pauli in 1930 to explain missing energy in beta decay
- Detected by Reines & Cowan in 1956 (nuclear reactor experiment)
- According to SM: electrically neutral, massless, weakly interacting

- Neutrino oscillations: evidence that neutrinos have mass
- **Physics beyond the Standard Model**

The Majorana Neutrino

- In the **Standard Model**, all the fermions are so-called **Dirac particles** and have an anti-fermion partner.
- In 1937 E. Majorana proposed that in the case of a neutral particle, the fermions and the anti-fermions could coincide. **The neutrino could therefore be a « Majorana particle ».**
- **A Majorana neutrino mass term could then be added to the Standard Model's Lagrangian**, and the « See-Saw » mechanism could explain the smallness of the mass of the three ordinary neutrinos by predicting at the same time three unstable heavy neutrinos. All neutrinos are predicted to be Majorana particles.

Majorana neutrino

With See-Saw mechanism
the small mass is
explained

Violation of the lepton
number conservation

Dirac neutrino

Lepton number
conservation

But why the mass is that
small ?

Pending question: neutrino is Dirac or Majorana?

Answering it is crucial for our understanding of particle physics and relevant for cosmology

Nuclear Double Beta Decay in a nutshell

Double Beta Decay is the **rarest nuclear weak process**

It takes place between **two even-even isobars**

If only electrons and nothing else:

$\times 10^{15}$

- Need to find single events in a ton of isotope x year(s) of exposure!
- 3×10^{-14} Bq/g
- We go to extreme length to limit ubiquitous radioactivity

15 Bq /
banana

Never observed \rightarrow **Half-life larger $> 10^{25}$ y - 10^{26} y**

More details on Double Beta Decay

Double beta decay is a nuclear transition involving two even-even isobars

$$\textcircled{1} \quad (A, Z) \rightarrow (A, Z+2) + 2e^- + 2\nu_e$$

Two-neutrino Double Beta Decay ($2\nu 2\beta$)
 allowed by the Standard Model
 already observed – $\tau \sim 10^{19} - 10^{21} \text{ y}$

$$\textcircled{2} \quad (A, Z) \rightarrow (A, Z+2) + 2e^-$$

Neutrinoless Double Beta Decay ($0\nu 2\beta$)
 never observed – $\tau > 10^{24} - 10^{26} \text{ y}$

Creation of matter without antimatter partners

- **Beyond Standard Model**
- **Lepton Number Violation (LNV)**

The only currently viable experimental approach to probe the **Majorana nature of neutrino**

More details on Double Beta Decay

Double beta decay is a nuclear transition involving two even-even isobars

Two-neutrino Double Beta Decay ($2\nu\beta\beta$)

allowed by the Standard Model
already observed – $\tau \sim 10^{19} - 10^{21}$ y

**Neutrinoless
Double Beta Decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$)**

never observed – $\tau > 10^{24} - 10^{26}$ y

Experimental signatures based on the

Sum energy spectrum of the two electrons

$Q_{\beta\beta} \sim 2\text{-}3 \text{ MeV}$

for the most promising candidates

Mechanisms behind Neutrinoless Double Beta Decay

Standard mechanism: neutrino physics

$0\nu 2\beta$ is mediated by

light massive Majorana neutrinos

(exactly those which oscillate)

Sometimes defined “**mass mechanism**”

Non-standard mechanisms:

Right currents, Sterile ν , SUSY R-parity, Leptoquarks, Kaluza-Klein,...

Not necessarily neutrino physics

- Minimal **straightforward extension** of the Standard Model
- **Metric** to compare experiments and technologies

Which and how many nuclei?

Double Beta Decay is the main decay channel for 35 nuclei, with a large span of $Q_{\beta\beta} \rightarrow$ energy available for the decay products

Rate in case of mass mechanism

How **0ν-DBD** is connected to **neutrino mixing matrix** and **masses** in case of process induced by light ν exchange (**mass mechanism**)

Majorana phases

$$m_{\beta\beta} = \left| |U_{e1}|^2 m_1 + e^{i\alpha_1} |U_{e2}|^2 m_2 + e^{i\alpha_2} |U_{e3}|^2 m_3 \right|$$

Phase space and nuclear matrix elements

$$1/\tau = G(Q,Z) g_A^4 |M_{\text{nucl}}|^2 \langle m_{\beta\beta} \rangle^2$$

leading term

$$\propto Z^2 Q_{\beta\beta}^5$$

Phase space

- Typically, a factor ~ 3 of spread for $|M_{\text{nucl}}|$ among the various models
- A spread of ~ 10 is expected in the half-life predictions
- Again a factor ~ 3 of spread is expected for $m_{\beta\beta}$

Working formula

Controversial

$$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} \simeq 10^{27-28} \left(\frac{0.01 \text{ eV}}{m_{\beta\beta}} \right)^2 \text{ yr}$$

NMEs encode the
of the parent
slides
ls

Phys. Rev. C 85, 034316 (2012)

with Christoph Wiesinger – TAUP 2025

The effective Majorana mass

A reference plot

$m_{\beta\beta}$ [meV]

1000

$$m_{\beta\beta} = \left| |U_{e1}|^2 m_1 + e^{i\alpha_1} |U_{e2}|^2 m_2 + e^{i\alpha_2} |U_{e3}|^2 m_3 \right|$$

100

Inverted Ordering (IO)

10

Normal Ordering (NO)

1

Width of bands:

- Majorana phases
- Uncertainty on ν oscillations parameters

Phys. Rev. D90, 033005 (2014)

1

10

100

Lightest neutrino mass [meV]

Experimental challenge

$m_{\beta\beta}$ [meV]

1000

100

10

1

50 meV

Inverted Ordering (IO)

15 meV

Normal Ordering (NO)

2.5 meV

$$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} \simeq 10^{27-28} \left(\frac{0.01 \text{ eV}}{m_{\beta\beta}} \right)^2 \text{ yr}$$

1

10

100

Lightest neutrino mass [meV]

$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} \sim 10^{26} \text{ y}$

$\sim 10 \text{ counts / (tonne y)}$
Reach of the **current** searches

$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} \sim 10^{27} \text{ y}$

$\sim 10 \text{ counts / (tonne 10y)}$
Reach of **next-generation** searches

$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} \sim 10^{28-29} \text{ y}$

$\sim 0.1 \text{ counts / (tonne 10y)}$
Next-to-next generation

Next generation

F: half-life sensitivity

Poisson limit

> 20 background counts

source mass live time energy resolution

$$F \propto (MT / b \Delta E)^{1/2}$$

background index

background counts @ $Q_{\beta\beta}$

$$M \times \Delta E \times T$$

Zero background

$$b \times M \times \Delta E \times T \ll 1$$

$$F \propto MT$$

Factors guiding isotope selection

➤ **High isotopic abundance (I.A.)**
and/or **easy enrichment**

➤ **High $Q_{\beta\beta}$**

Larger phase space:
 $G(Q,Z) \propto Z^2 Q^5$

Easier background control

➤ **Compatibility with a beneficial detection technique**

- High energy resolution
- Background identification
- Efficiency and scalability

General features for $0\nu 2\beta$ searches

Requests for the source

① **Large source** → tonne scale → $> 10^{27}$ nuclei

② **Maximize efficiency**

→ The option in which the source is separated from the detector (NEMO-3 – SuperNEMO approach) is abandoned for next-generation experiments

SuperNEMO demonstrator is now running at LSM

Source \subseteq Detector

Source \neq Detector

Physics results with 6.11 kg of ^{82}Se

- $0\nu\beta\beta$ search in multiple modes
- $2\nu\beta\beta$ spectrum study:
 - Nuclear physics (g_A , excited states, NME)
 - Exotic $2\nu\beta\beta$ decays (V+A, bosonic neutrinos..)

Requests for the background

Generic measures as underground operation, shielding (passive and active), radiopurity of materials, vetos are common to $0\nu 2\beta$ and other rare event search

Specific desirable features for $0\nu 2\beta$

- High energy resolution
- Particle identification
- Tracking / Event topology
- Multi-site vs. single-site events
- Surface vs. bulk events
- Fiducial volume / Active shielding
- Final-state nucleus identification

Currently competing technologies

①

Source dilution in a liquid scintillator

KamLAND-Zen (^{136}Xe) – SNO+ (^{130}Te)

- Re-use of existing infrastructures
- Large amount of isotopes (multi-ton)
- Isotope dilution (a few %)
- Energy resolution $\sim 10\%$ FWHM
- Rough space resolution

②

TPCs

EXO-200 – NEXT stages – nEXO (^{136}Xe)

- Large amount of isotopes (multi-ton)
- Full isotope concentration
- Energy resolution $\sim 1\% - 2\%$ FWHM
- Event topology

③

Semiconductor detectors

GERDA – LEGEND (^{76}Ge)

- Crystal array (~ 1 ton scale in total)
- (Almost) full isotope concentration
- Energy resolution $\sim 0.1\% - 0.2\%$ FWHM
- Particle identification
- Pulse shape discrimination

④

Bolometers

CUORE (^{130}Te) – AMoRE – CUPID (^{100}Mo)

Liquids and gases

Single crystals

Currently competing technologies

① Source dilution in a liquid scintillator

KamLAND-Zen (^{136}Xe) – EXO-200 (^{136}Xe)

- Re-use of existing infrastructures
- Large amount of isotopes (multi-ton)
- Isotope dilution (a few %)
- Energy resolution $\sim 10\%$ FWHM

② TPCs

EXO-200 – NEXT stage

Take-away messages:

- The best detector technology does not exist
- The combination of readout channels is very welcome (exemple: good resolution with one, background rejection with the other)

③ Semiconductor detectors

GERDA – LEGEND (^{76}Ge)

- Crystal array (~ 1 ton scale in total)
- (Almost) full isotope concentration
- Energy resolution $\sim 0.1\%$ - 0.2% FWHM
- Particle identification
- Pulse shape discrimination

④ Bolometers

CUORE (^{130}Te) – AMoRE – CUPID (^{100}Mo)

Single crystals

Experimental status

KamLAND-Zen 800 - $T_{1/2} > 3.8 \times 10^{26}$ y
[arXiv:2406.11438 (2024)]

GERDA - $T_{1/2} > 1.8 \times 10^{26}$ y
[Phys. Rev. Lett. 125, 252502 (2020)]

EXO-200 - $T_{1/2} > 3.5 \times 10^{25}$ y
[Phys. Rev. Lett. 123, 161802] (2019)

MAJORANA dem. - $T_{1/2} > 8.3 \times 10^{25}$ y
[Phys. Rev. Lett. 130, 062501 (2023)]

CUORE - $T_{1/2} > 3.5 \times 10^{25}$ y
[TAUP 2025 (2025)]

CUPID-0 - $T_{1/2} > 4.6 \times 10^{24}$ y
[Phys. Rev. Lett. 129, 111801 (2022)]

AMORE-I - $T_{1/2} > 2.9 \times 10^{24}$ y
[Phys. Rev. Lett. 134, 082501 (2025)]

CUPID-Mo - $T_{1/2} > 1.8 \times 10^{24}$ y
[Eur. Phys. J. C 82, 1033 (2022)]

NEMO-3 - $T_{1/2} > 1.1 \times 10^{24}$ y
[Phys. Rev. D 92, 072011 (2015)]

$T_{1/2} > 10^{24}$ y 90% C.I.
restricted club

Waiting for next generation!
LEGEND200 already in data taking
[1.9×10^{26} y]

KamLAND-Zen

- **1000 ton liquid scintillator detector**
- Re-use facility used for ν oscillation experiment
- **Nylon balloon with ^{enr}Xe -loaded scintillator**
- **KamLAND-Zen-800, 2nd phase**

- **Large isotope mass, 750 kg of 91% ^{136}Xe**
- **Poor energy resolution, 4% at 2.5 MeV**
- ➔ Final result, **world-best constraint**
 - $T_{1/2}(^{136}\text{Xe}) > 3.8 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ yr}$ (90% CL)
 - ➔ $m_{\beta\beta} < [28, 122] \text{ meV}$ (90% CL)
 - $> 2.6 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ yr}$ (90% CL, sensitivity)

- **KamLAND2-Zen, planned detector upgrade**

➔ After 5 years: $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 2 \times 10^{27} \text{ yr}$

SNO+

[arXiv:2403.19351 (2024)]

- **780 ton liquid scintillator detector**
Re-use facility used for solar ν experiment
- **Staged ^{nat}Te loading**
 - **Large isotope mass,**
e.g. 1.3 ton of ^{130}Te for 0.5% loading
 - **Poor energy resolution, 4% at 2.5 MeV**
- Water phase completed, scintillator phase ongoing, **0.5% loading in preparation**

→ Projected sensitivity

$$T_{1/2}(^{130}\text{Te}) > 1.8 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ yr (90\% CL), 3 yr with 0.5\%}$$

$$T_{1/2}(^{130}\text{Te}) > 7.4 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ yr (90\% CL), 5 yr with 1.5\%}$$

Background budget
(low concentration → dominated by ^8B solar ν)

nEXO

- **Liquid ^{136}Xe time projection chamber,**
 - building on EXO-200
 - **Large isotope mass, 5 ton of 90% ^{136}Xe**
 - **Reasonable energy resolution, 1% at 2.5 MeV**

➔ Projected sensitivity, 10 yr

[Adhikari et al., J.Phys.G 49 (2022) 1, 015104]

$$T_{1/2}(^{136}\text{Xe}) > 1.35 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ yr (90\% CL)}$$

$$T_{1/2}(^{136}\text{Xe}) = 7.4 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ yr (3}\sigma) \quad \text{Discovery sensitivity}$$

- **Development of Ba tagging**

[Chambers et al., Nature 569 (2019) 7755, 203-207;

Ray et al., Atoms 12 (2024) 12, 71]

Background dominated by Rn outgassing and intrinsic radioactivity

NEXT

→ Joshua Grocott, Jan 7

- **High pressure (10-15 bar) gas ^{enr}Xe TPC**
 - Primary scintillation ($t_0 \rightarrow z$ coordinate)
 - Electroluminescence for energy resolution and for tracking

Staged approach

- **NEXT-White (2015-2021) – LSC, Spain**
5 kg prototype

- **NEXT-100 (2023-2029) – LSC, Spain**

Upscaling of NEXT-White → 97 kg

- Currently, operation at 4 bar
- Operation at 10 bar by 2026
- Good energy resolution <1%

Projected sensitivity

$T_{1/2}(^{136}\text{Xe}) > 4 \cdot 10^{25} \text{ yr}$ (90% CL) – 3 year

[JHEP 2016, 159 (2016)]

- **NEXT-HD (High Definition) – start in 2030**
Up to 1 ton enriched Xe gas at 20 bar

Target sensitivity: 10^{27} y

5 ton \times y

- **NEXT-BOLD (Barium On Light Detection)**
 - Ba tagging by **SMFI** (Single Molecule Fluorescence Imaging) was proved – demonstrator under R&D
 - Background free [JINST 18 P08006 (2023)]

Target sensitivity: 10^{28} y

10 ton \times y

LEGEND

➤ High-purity ^{enr}Ge detectors in active liquid argon shield, building on:

- GERDA, **lowest background**, background-free [Agostini et al., PRL 125 (2020) 25, 2525 02]
- MAJORANA, **best energy resolution**, 2.5 keV (FWHM) at 2.0 MeV [Arnquist et al., PRL 130 (2023) 6, 062501]

➤ **LEGEND-200**, up to 200 kg of 90% ^{76}Ge in

- Upgraded GERDA infrastructure, improved light read-out
- Data taking

→ Projected discovery sensitivity, 5 yr

[Agostini et al., Rev.Mod.Phys. 95 (2023) 2, 025002]

$$T_{1/2}(^{76}\text{Ge}) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ yr } (3\sigma)$$

➤ **LEGEND-1000**, new infrastructure in preparation at LNGS

- **Sizeable isotope mass**, 1 ton of 90% ^{76}Ge

→ Projected discovery sensitivity, 10 yr

[Abgrall et al., arXiv:2107.11462]

$$T_{1/2}(^{76}\text{Ge}) > 1.6 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ yr } (90\% \text{ CL})$$

$$T_{1/2}(^{76}\text{Ge}) = 1.3 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ yr } (3\sigma)$$

CUORE

CUORE - LNGS, Italy

- Array of natural TeO_2 crystals operated as bolometers at 10 mK
 - Built on the precursor CUORICINO experiment
 - 988 TeO_2 crystals, arranged in 19 towers – 206 kg of ^{130}Te
 - Energy resolution $\Delta E \sim 7.8$ keV FWHM @ $Q_{\beta\beta}$

Results: $T_{1/2} > 3.5 \times 10^{25}$ y (90%) – 2039 kg y
[TAUP 2025]

Background dominated by energy-degraded surface α 's

→ Roberto Serino, Jan 7

CUPID demonstrators

CUPID-Mo - LSM, France

- Pure bolometers → Scintillating bolometers
- ^{130}Te (TeO_2) → ^{100}Mo (enriched Li_2MoO_4)
 $Q_{\beta\beta} = 3034$ keV > 2.6 MeV (Reject external γ background)
- 20 Li_2Mo_4 crystals – 2.26 kg of ^{100}Mo
- Energy resolution $\Delta E \sim 7.7$ keV FWHM @ $Q_{\beta\beta}$

Results:
 $T_{1/2} > 1.8 \times 10^{24}$ y (90%)
2.71 kg y

Reject
 α background

CUPID-0 - LNGS, Italy
First scintillating
bolometer demonstrator

Zn^{82}Se

[PRL, 129, 111801 (2022)]

$T_{1/2} > 4.6 \times 10^{24}$ y

CUPID

enrMo-containing scintillating bolometers

- Heat readout based on **NTD Ge sensors**
- Energy resolution $\Delta E \sim 5 \text{ keV FWHM @ } Q_{\beta\beta}$
- Exploit CUORE infrastructure changing isotope
- Adopt CUPID-Mo technology
- Single module: $\text{Li}_2^{100}\text{MoO}_4$ **45×45×45 mm – 280 g**
- **1596 crystals**
- **240 kg of ^{100}Mo** with >95% enrichment
- **Bolometric Ge light detectors** as in CUPID-Mo, CUPID-0
Upgraded with **Neganov-Trofimov-Luke (NTL) mode**
to achieve the required rejection of $2\nu 2\beta$ random
coincidences [**BINGO/CROSS development**]

[Eur. Phys. J. C 85, 737 (2025)]

→ NTL Light detectors under test in the
CROSS demonstrator [arxiv.org/abs/2507.15732]

Single tower
14 floors

Single floor

CUPID – Timeline and sensitivity

➤ Staged development

- Stage-I → 1/3 of crystals (2030-2033)
- Stage-II → remaining 2/3 of crystals (2034)

CUPID Stage-I

- **median discovery sensitivity**
(3 y livetime - 80 kg ^{100}Mo + 5 keV FWHM)
 $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} = 0.2 \times 10^{27} \text{ yr}$
 $m_{\beta\beta} < (25-44) \text{ meV}$ [arXiv:2504.14369]

FULL CUPID

- **Exclusion sensitivity 90% C.I.**
(10 y livetime - 240 kg ^{100}Mo + 5 keV FWHM)
 $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 1.4 \times 10^{27} \text{ yr}$
 $m_{\beta\beta} < (9.6-16) \text{ meV}$
- **median discovery sensitivity**
 $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} = 1 \times 10^{27} \text{ yr}$
 $m_{\beta\beta} < (12-21) \text{ meV}$

R&D ongoing to reduce the BI by a further order of magnitude (BINGO and others), making possible

- **CUPID-1T**²⁷
10 y livetime - 1000 kg ^{100}Mo + 5 keV FWHM
 $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 1 \times 10^{28} \text{ yr}$
 $m_{\beta\beta} < (3.8-6.3) \text{ meV}$ Deep inside the normal ordering region

→ Nuclear Shell Model is not considered

Beyond CUORE and CUPID: BINGO

Techniques for background rejection in future Li_2MoO_4 / TeO_2 based experiments

3 main innovations

[NIMA 1069 (2024) 169936]

- **Internal active shield** (ultrapure BGO scintillators)
 - mitigate γ background in TeO_2
- **Revolutionary assembly** to reject surface background
- **Enhanced-sensitivity (Neganov-Trofimov-Luke)** light detectors
 - mitigate pile-up
 - read out the BGO active shields
 - detect Cherenkov light in TeO_2

MINI-BINGO in Modane (demonstrator)

12 Li_2MoO_4 crystals

12 TeO_2 crystals

from 2026

Simulation CUPID vs. BINGO

How we are moving forward

Current generation
(final sensitivity for
concluded/running
projects)

Next generation
(projects to be
started on 5-10 years'
time scale)

Other challenging ideas

Non-exhausting list of novel projects

- **LEGEND-6000** – ^{76}Ge - A multi-ton evolution of the LEGEND program
133 detector strings – 6 tons of ^{76}Ge – $\sim 10^{29}$ yr sensitivity
- **Dual phase Xe TPC** – ^{136}Xe → *Chiara Capelli, Jan 9*
XLZD – $\sim 5.7 \times 10^{27}$ - yr sensitivity → *Ricardo Peres, Jan 7*
- **TINY** – Bolometers containing ^{96}Zr and/or ^{150}Nd – very favorable isotopes – high energy resolution
- **SELENA** – ^{82}Se - Amorphous ^{82}Se deposited onto large area CMOS – pixelization, tracking
Excellent background rejection – Industrial construction, multi ton – $\sim 10^{29}$ yr sensitivity
- **JUNO ($\beta\beta$ upgrade)** – ^{136}Xe
Re-use JUNO infrastructure - 5 – 50 tons of ^{136}Xe inside a balloon - $\sim 10^{27}$ - 10^{28} yr sensitivity
- **THEIA** – ^{130}Te → *Gabriel Orebi Gann, Jan 8*
A **hybrid water-based liquid scintillator** 25 kton detector with isotope loading - 10^{28} yr sensitivity
- **NuDoubt++** → *Kira Mossel, Jan 8*
Dedicated to $\beta+\beta+$ - **scintillator + Cherekov** – **Opaque scintillator** – Positron identification

Conclusions

- $0\nu\beta\beta$ is a crucial process for particle physics and cosmology
- Several approaches and technologies make this field very active
- Many projects will extend their sensitivity in the next years
- Next-generation experiments have a good discovery potential

Neutrinoless double beta decay is a high-risk, high-reward pursuit

A hard search, but a discovery would reshape physics:
the Standard Model, neutrino mass, and the matter–antimatter asymmetry.

What lies ahead

From the current to the next generation

Emphasis on **7 promising research lines**

- | | | | | |
|---|---|----------------------------|--|-------------------------------------|
| ① | KamLAND-Zen 400 → KamLAND-Zen 800 → KamLAND2-Zen | ^{136}Xe | Source dilution in a liquid scintillator | |
| ② | SNO+ → SNO+-phase II | ^{130}Te | | |
| ③ | EXO-200 → nEXO | ^{136}Xe | Xe TPCs | |
| ④ | NEXT-White → NEXT-100 → NEXT-HD / NEXT-BOLD | | | |
| ⑤ | { GERDA
MAJORANA dem. } | → LEGEND-200 → LEGEND-1000 | ^{76}Ge | Semiconductor detectors – Ge diodes |
| ⑥ | AMORE-I → AMORE-II | ^{100}Mo | Bolometers | |
| ⑦ | { CUORE ^{130}Te
CUPID-Mo ^{100}Mo
CUPID-0 ^{82}Se } | → CUPID → CUPID 1t | | ^{100}Mo |

AMoRE

enrMo-containing scintillating bolometers

- Heat readout based on **MMC sensors**
- Energy resolution $\Delta E \sim 10\text{-}15 \text{ keV FWHM @} Q_{\beta\beta}$

➤ AMoRE-I (2020-2022)

- 13x $^{48\text{depl}}\text{Ca}^{100}\text{MoO}_4$ (4.6 kg)
- 5x $\text{Li}_2^{100}\text{MoO}_4$ (1.6 kg)

Results: $T_{1/2} > 2.9 \times 10^{24} \text{ y}$

[Phys. Rev. Lett. 134, 082501 (2025)]

➤ AMORE-II – from 2026 – phased approach

- Secured **110 kg of ^{100}Mo** – 596x $\text{Li}_2^{100}\text{MoO}_4$ crystals
- New cryostat and underground lab – work in progress

Projected sensitivity: $8 \times 10^{26} \text{ y}$ in 5 years

Neutrino mass scale and effective neutrino mass

Cosmology, **single** and **double β decay** measure different combinations of the neutrino mass eigenvalues, constraining the neutrino mass scale

$$\Sigma \equiv \sum_{i=1}^3 m_i$$

Cosmology- simple sum - pure kinematical effect

$$\langle m_{\beta} \rangle \equiv \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 m_i^2 |U_{ei}|^2 \right)^{1/2}$$

β Decay – KATRIN - incoherent sum - real neutrino

$$\langle m_{\beta\beta} \rangle \equiv \left| \sum_{i=1}^3 m_i |U_{ei}|^2 e^{i\alpha_i} \right|$$

double β decay - coherent sum - virtual neutrino - Majorana phases

Many theoretical models for the nuclear matrix elements

WE WANT YOU

$$1/\tau = G(Q,Z) g_A^4 |M_{\text{nucl}}|^2 \langle m_{\beta\beta} \rangle^2$$

The $0\nu\beta\beta$ community in general assumes $g_A \approx 1.27$ (no quenching)

- Different **phenomenological many-body methods** using different approximations (e.g. limited number of nuclear shells), **significant spread**

[Agostini et al., Rev.Mod.Phys. 95 (2023) 2, 025002; ..]

- Experiments provide **range of $m_{\beta\beta}$ constraints**

$$T_{1/2} = .. \rightarrow m_{\beta\beta} = [.., ..]$$

- **First ab initio calculations available**, may resolve quenching issue

[Yao et al., PRL 124 (2020); Belley et al., PRL 126 (2021); Novario et al., PRL 126 (2021); Cirigliano et al., PRL 120 (2018); Belley et al., arXiv:2307.15156; Belley et al., PRL 132 (2024); ..]

- Effective field theory (EFT) analysis identified additional **short-range contribution**

[Cirigliano et al., PRL 120 (2018) 20, 202001; ..]

Credit Christoph Wiesinger – TAUP 2025

CUPID - background

Dominant contributions: **pile-up events**
(random coincidences of ordinary $2\nu\beta\beta$ events)

➤ **Data driven:**
based on CUORE and CUPID-Mo background models
[Phys. Rev. D 110 (2024) 052003] [Eur. Phys. J. C 83 (2023) 675]

Conservative projections based on
current available data: **BI = 1.1×10^{-4} cckky**

- **Fastest $2\nu 2\beta$ decay: $T_{1/2} \sim 7.1 \times 10^{18}$ y**
- **Slow response of bolometric signals**
Mitigated by Neganov-Trofimov-Luke light detectors

**Two orders of magnitude
better than in CUORE**

Currently competing technologies (3)

